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**A TALE OF TWO DUSTS:
MIMICKING SITE-SPECIFIC SOILING DYNAMICS AND CLEANING APPROACHES FOR PV PLANTS**

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ABSTRACT: Replicating and understanding site-specific soiling dynamics is crucial for optimizing PV designs and modelling, in-field soiling monitoring and cleaning strategies. This study discusses a multi-parameter testing protocol for soiling and cleaning of PV modules, under controlled conditions using dust samples from two distinct environments: the Atacama Desert and Southern France. A novel experimental setup, incorporating a soiling and cleaning chamber, was employed to replicate real-world deposition and removal processes. The impact of soiling was assessed through I-V characterization, comparing different PV module configurations. Results indicate that anti-soiling and anti-reflective coatings mitigate optical losses more effectively than standard glass covers, whereas encapsulant choice has a negligible effect in soiling-induced optical losses. Cleaning tests revealed that high brush rotation speeds with soft bristles yielded the highest efficiency (68.2%). Additionally, the study successfully simulated desert cementation processes, validating the accelerated testing methodology. These findings provide valuable insights for optimizing PV maintenance strategies and enhancing module design, contributing to improved energy yield in soiling-prone regions.

Keywords: *PV systems; soiling; soiling losses; soiling mitigation.*

1 INTRODUCTION: CONTEXT and AIM

Photovoltaic (PV) systems, especially in soiling-prone sites such as in arid dusty regions, marine/coastal environments and sites near intense agricultural activities, suffer significant energy losses due to soiling. These losses can reach 20% to 30% per year, resulting in financial losses exceeding €10 billion in 2023 [1]. The behaviour and impact of soiling vary widely depending on environmental conditions, the dust composition, and the properties of PV materials. Regional factors such as dust origin, particle size, hydrophobicity, and mineral content all play critical roles in determining how soiling mechanisms develop and how effectively they can be mitigated [2]. Despite its importance, the influence of these diverse variables is not yet fully understood nor quantified, particularly when comparing starkly different climatic and environmental contexts. Therefore, next to advanced tools for in-field soiling monitoring and assessment, it is essential to develop indoor (“accelerated”) soiling testing protocols, in order to mimic dust deposition (and eventual soiling losses) in controlled environment, under the combined influence of environmental and PV parameters. Understanding exactly such site- or climate- specific soiling dynamics, can, in turn, help PV industry in developing optimized soiling mitigation strategies at O&M level, as well as reinforce PV modules’ resilience against soiling, at design level.

The Atacama Desert and Southern France represent two regions with vastly distinct environmental conditions and dust characteristics. The Atacama, one of the driest places on Earth, produces fine, hydrophobic dust particles that tend to adhere stubbornly to PV surfaces. In contrast, the dust in Southern France is generally coarser and more mineral-rich, with its soiling behaviour influenced by Mediterranean humidity and seasonal variability. These differences present an opportunity to study how dust

properties and environmental conditions affect soiling losses, adhesion, and cleaning efficacy.

In this study, we employ a novel setup for accelerated soiling and cleaning tests of two distinct dust samples from the aforementioned regions. Through the designed testing protocol, overall aim of the study is to mimic soiling dynamics and evaluate cleaning strategies for PV modules, in controlled laboratory conditions, under the influence of: i) different bill of materials (BOMs) selection, ii) different environmental conditions and iii) different cleaning parameters. By systematically comparing and quantifying soiling dynamics and cleaning parameters, our end-goal is to draw valuable conclusions and insights into the interaction of PV site-specific factors with soiling and cleaning processes, to further guide towards streamlined O&M for soiling-prone PV plants.

2 METHODOLOGY – APPROACH

Two specific test benches developed and operating at CEA [3] were employed in this study (Fig. 1): a soiling chamber (Fig. 1, top) and a cleaning chamber (Fig. 1, bottom). For all the designed tests, the impact of soiling is evaluated through I-V characterization of the tested PV laminates under standard test conditions (STC), using a Class A+ PASAN solar simulator. The soiling chamber, equipped with a dust generator, enables the homogeneous and repeatable soiling of PV modules. A precise mass of pre-dehydrated dust is loaded into a piston, which forms part of the dust generator and ensures accurate control over the volume flow of injected dust. Carried by dry air at a controlled pressure, the dust is directed onto a deflector, creating a dust cloud within the chamber. This suspended dust gradually settles on the modules placed on the sample holder plate, which can be tilted between 0° and 90°. This process completes a fully controlled soiling operation,

referred to as an "injection". The chamber also includes various devices for adjusting key parameters such as temperature and humidity during testing. The interior temperature can be regulated between 15°C and 50°C, the temperature of the sample holder plate can be set between 10°C and 50°C, and the relative humidity can be controlled up to 90%.

The studied samples, also fabricated at CEA-INES facilities, comprise of "mini PV modules" (i.e. single-cell PV laminates), with silicon heterojunction (SHJ) solar cells, in different bill of materials (BOM) combinations in terms of front cover coatings and encapsulants.

Figure 1: The lab setup at CEA-INES developed and employed for controlled replication of soiling, cleaning tests and dust characterization. Top: the soiling chamber and its different components. Bottom-left: External view of the cleaning chamber. Bottom-Right: Inside view of the cleaning chamber.

The entire experimental sequence applied, for the **soiling study**, consists of four main steps: 1) Electrical characterization (I_{sc} and P_{max}) and transmittance measurements of PV laminate-sample and glass sample at clean state (reference measurements); 2) Soiling injection; 3) Post-soiling measurements; 4) Manual cleaning of PV laminate, return to clean state.

For the case of the **cleaning study**, we have assessed 4 parameters with 3 configurations for each of them, as summarized in Table 1. It should be noted that, in the present study, we focus only on dry (waterless) cleaning. Follow-up work and results will also assess water-based cleaning sequences.

Parameters	Conf. 1	Conf. 2	Conf. 3
A : Robot moving speed	50 mm/s	250 mm/s	500 mm/s
B : Brush rotation speed	0 tour/min	100 tour/min	550 tour/min
C : Brush type	Rigid nylon	Soft nylon	horse hair (very soft)
D : front sheet	Solar	AR	Transparent

Two distinctively different types of dust (soiling) samples were applied and studied in this work. **Dust 1** originates from actual soiling collected in a utility-scale PV plant site located in southern France. This site has been identified by CNR (SERENDI-PV partner and PV plant owner) as susceptible to soiling due to its proximity to a quarry as well as to significant agricultural activity, both generating relatively important levels of soiling, in a region with generally little rainfall ("hot dry-summer"

climate, classified as *Csa*, per the Köppen climate classification). A total 12 kg of dust/soiling was collected and sieved with a 1.6mm mesh, to be then used for the experiment. For each soiling injection experiment with Dust 1, we have adjusted the test chamber's environmental parameters taking into account typical site-specific conditions and the limits of the artificial soiling equipment:

1. 3g of dust injected (approximately 0.12 mg/cm²), relative humidity (RH) > 80% and temperature of sample T_{sample} 17°C, (dew conditions).
2. 5g of dust injected (approximately 0.2 mg/cm²), RH > 80% and T_{sample} 17°C (dew conditions).
3. 5g of dust injected (approximately 0.2 mg/cm²), RH < 30% and T_{sample} 30°C (dry conditions).

Dust 2 originates from the Plataforma Solar del Desierto de Atacama (PSDA, for its acronym in Spanish). The PSDA is located in the Atacama Desert (24.09°S, 69.93°W) at an altitude of 963 meters above sea level, in a region classified as a cold and arid desert (BWk). The samples were exposed in the soiling chamber, specifically programmed to replicate the atmospheric conditions of the PSDA. To achieve this, meteorological data collected over a year was used, considering solar resource, temperature (°C), and relative humidity (RH) to generate a representative typical day. Based on this typical day, cycles were established to simulate nighttime conditions—characterized by high relative humidity (>70%) and low temperatures (~7°C)—while daytime conditions were recreated with high temperatures (>30°C) and low relative humidity (~40%). This indoor process was carried out in three sequential stages: (1) dust deposition, (2) simulated humidity condensation, and (3) final cementation. These conditions were applied sequentially to the samples, enabling the analysis of accelerated soiling effects under controlled laboratory conditions.

3 RESULTS and DISCUSSION

The **soiling study** of **Dust 1** was carried out for seven different BOM scenarios of tested PV laminates, in order to first quantify (and understand) the individual impact of soiling buildup on optical (and therefore power output) PV losses, for: i) different front cover (glass) coatings and ii) for different encapsulant types. So far, after a single soiling injection with **Dust 1** sample, results indicate soiling losses in the range of 3% to 5%, highly dependent on the type of front cover coating of the tested PV laminates. In particular, samples with white glass as front cover present the higher soiling losses, whereas PV laminates with anti-soiling (AS) and anti-reflective (AR) coatings on their front cover, as well as with hydrophobic (HPB) ones, seem to better "resist" against optical/current losses from soiling buildup (Fig. 2). On the other hand, the choice of the encapsulant plays minimal role to the light management and, eventually, the resulting optical/current losses from soiling, for the tested PV laminates, for the case of Dust 1. The slight absolute difference (0.5%) observed between the soiling losses for the two encapsulant types in comparison (Fig. 2) can be considered negligible, particularly with regard to the intrinsic uncertainty related to the experimental protocol. These observations are suggestive of the need to dissociate the PV laminates

solely according to the nature and coating of their front cover.

Figure 2: Relative soiling (current losses) for all PV laminates subjected to the indoor soiling testing protocol with Dust 1. Comparative results (bottom) for different bill of materials used for seven different samples (top).

For the *cleaning study* of *Dust 1*, we have employed three of the tested PV laminates and performed three identical cleaning tests for each configuration. Prior to each cleaning sequence, each PV laminate was soiled with the same conditions and scale of dust particles (<35 μm) that were already used in the soiling study. The amount of dust deposited on each module is around 0.25 mg/cm², which corresponds to an *I_{sc}* loss of around 4.5%. The impact after each operation soiling and cleaning is assessed by measuring the *I_{sc}*, under STC, with the employed solar simulator. Preliminary results (Fig. 3), for the case of Dust 1 and the cleaning configurations described in Table 1, are suggestive of the higher average cleaning efficiency (68.2%) of Configuration 3, in comparison with that of Configurations 1 and 2 (25.1% and 41.9% respectively). From the results, we may also conclude that the process in Configuration 3 is significantly more repeatable, whereas it is preferable to use a high brush rotation speed, with brush made of soft bristles (e.g. horsehair), the latter being better suited to protect the PV modules' front cover coatings that are often sensitive to abrasion. Besides, such configuration allows also the cleaning cart to be driven at high speeds, which, in practice, can contribute to significant reduction in cleaning time and costs.

Figure 3: Comparative results for the cleaning efficiency of the three applied test configurations: Indicative results for the case of *Dust 1*, for the configurations described in section 2.

This section presents the preliminary results obtained in the study using *Dust 2*, a more detailed analysis and comparative discussion will be included in a future study. The deposition results, simulating the PSDA conditions, were analyzed using a FE-SEM Zeiss Sigma 360 scanning electron microscope. The analysis revealed well-defined prismatic particles, as shown in Fig. 4. The absence of erosion signs in these particles indicates the occurrence of a recrystallization process of soluble material. The high-humidity cycles during the night and high temperatures in the morning, replicated by the soiling chamber, facilitated crystal formation, recreating phenomena observed in real outdoor conditions, such as the formation of the well-known "desert rose."

Figure 4: Top: Soiling sample obtained by sieving PSDA dust ("*Dust 2*"). Middle: Cemented soiling sample deposited on a module using the soiling chamber. Bottom: EDS image of the soiling sample deposited on a module using the soiling chamber.2.

Elemental analysis (Fig. 4, bottom) confirms these results, showing that the crystals are primarily composed

of sulfur and calcium, indicating the presence of gypsum, a compound previously documented at the PSDA by Olivares et al [4]. Additionally, silicon was detected, associated with quartz, one of the most abundant materials in the desert. This quartz becomes trapped within the gypsum, clearly evidencing the cementation process. The soiling chamber demonstrated its ability to replicate the cementation process observed at the PSDA, achieving the effects of nighttime high humidity cycles and daytime high temperatures in a shorter period. This controlled environment allowed the formation of consolidated deposits like those found in real conditions, validating its effectiveness in accelerating and reproducing the deposition and recrystallization mechanisms characteristic of the region.

The *soiling study* for *Dust 2* was conducted on four samples to evaluate the impact of dust accumulation on optical and electrical losses. Results (Fig. 5) indicate an average decrease of the I_{sc} by 5%, for each increase in deposition density, which ranged between 0.45 mg/cm² and 1.15 mg/cm². Regarding optical losses, transmittance reductions were observed across the spectral range of 350 to 1100 nm, reaching 50% in samples with the highest dust density. Comparison with previous studies conducted at the PSDA indicates strong agreement with data obtained under real outdoor exposure conditions, particularly in material deposition patterns, accumulated dust density, and optical transmittance reduction [4].

Figure 5: Top: Short-circuit current losses as a function of surface dust density. Bottom: Transmittance losses correspond to increasing dust density in each deposition: Indicative results for the case of *Dust 2*.

4 CONCLUSIONS - OUTLOOK

This work demonstrates the feasibility and relevance of employing accelerated soiling and cleaning protocols to

systematically investigate the impact of site-specific dust characteristics and environmental conditions on PV module performance. By comparing dust samples from Southern France and the Atacama Desert, we highlighted the strong influence of dust morphology, mineral composition, and associated climatic conditions on soiling losses and cleaning efficiency. Results with Dust 1 (Southern France) indicate that front cover coatings play a much more critical role in mitigating soiling-induced losses than encapsulant choice, while dry cleaning efficiency is significantly improved when employing high brush rotation speeds with soft bristles. For Dust 2 (Atacama Desert), controlled indoor testing successfully replicated the cementation phenomena observed in outdoor conditions, reproducing gypsum recrystallization and dust consolidation under alternating humidity and temperature cycles. The agreement with outdoor data validates the effectiveness of the accelerated soiling protocol as a reliable surrogate for field exposure.

The study emphasizes that no universal soiling mitigation strategy can be applied across sites, as dust origin and environmental context fundamentally govern soiling dynamics and cleaning requirements. Instead, site-specific knowledge should drive both O&M strategies and PV material design. Future work will expand the testing framework by:

- extending cleaning studies to include water-based methods and hybrid approaches,
- assessing long-term durability of front cover coatings under repeated soiling/cleaning cycles, and
- refining the soiling protocols by integrating real-time outdoor data for more accurate climate-to-lab translation.

Ultimately, advancing such accelerated testing approaches can bridge the gap between laboratory investigations and real-world PV performance, thereby supporting the development of optimized, climate-tailored solutions to minimize soiling-induced energy and financial losses.

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